

DGIP-CEDS

Data Governance and Intellectual Property Governance
in Common European Data Spaces

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European Health Data Space: Legal Pitfalls for Data Protection and IP Management

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Presentation overview

European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation

Key objectives

- lays down **common rules and mechanisms** for primary use of electronic health data and secondary use of electronic health data in the EU
- establishes a **cross-border infrastructure** for primary and secondary use of electronic health data in the EU
- establishes **governance and coordination mechanisms** at EU and national level:
 - each EU Member State shall designate one or more *digital health authorities (DHAs)* responsible for primary use of electronic health data
 - each EU Member State shall designate one or more *health data access bodies (HDABs)* responsible for secondary use of electronic health data

(Most relevant provisions will apply from 2029.)

1) 'Electronic health data'

Definitions

- Article 2(2)(a) '**personal electronic health data**' means data concerning health and genetic data, processed in an electronic form;
 - 'genetic data' vs 'omics data'
 - data protection problems relating to common genetic data
- Article 2(2)(b) '**non-personal electronic health data**' means electronic health data other than personal electronic health data, including both data that have been anonymised so that they no longer relate to an identified or identifiable natural person (the 'data subject') and data that have never related to a data subject;
 - no clear distinction between 'non-personal data' and 'non-personal electronic health data'
 - 'anonymised data' vs 'anonymously collected data'

2) Secondary use of electronic health data and opt-out

Minimum categories of electronic health data for secondary use

Article 51(1) **Health data holders shall make the following categories of electronic health data available for secondary use** [.]:

- (a) electronic health data from EHRs;
- (b) data on factors impacting on health, including socioeconomic, environmental and behavioural determinants of health;
- (c) **aggregated data** on healthcare needs, resources allocated to healthcare, the provision of and access to healthcare, healthcare expenditure and financing;
- (d) data on pathogens that impact human health;
- (e) healthcare-related administrative data, including on dispensations, reimbursement claims and reimbursements;
- (f) human genetic, epigenomic and genomic data;**
- (g) other human molecular data such as proteomic, transcriptomic, metabolomic, lipidomic and **other omic data;**
- (h) personal electronic health data automatically generated through medical devices;**
- (i) data from wellness applications;**
- (j) data on professional status, and on the specialisation and institution of health professionals involved in the treatment of a natural person;
- (k) data from population-based health data registries such as public health registries;
- (l) data from medical registries and mortality registries;
- (m) **data from clinical trials, clinical studies, clinical investigations and performance studies** subject to Regulation (EU) No 536/2014, Regulation (EU) 2024/1938 of the European Parliament and of the Council (35), Regulation (EU) 2017/745 and Regulation (EU) 2017/746;
- (n) other health data from medical devices;
- (o) data from registries for medicinal products and medical devices;
- (p) data from research cohorts, questionnaires and surveys related to health, after the first publication of the related results;
- (q) health data from biobanks and associated databases.**

2) Secondary use of electronic health data and opt-out

Opt-out

General rule (opt-out):

- Article 71(1) **Natural persons shall have the right to opt out** at any time, and without providing any reason, from the processing of personal electronic health data relating to them for secondary use under [the EHDS]. The exercise of that right shall be reversible.
 - data representativeness and data biases?
 - potential legal conflicts and fragmentations?

Exception (no opt-out):

- Article 71(5) The rules on any mechanism to implement **exceptions** [...] from paragraph 1 shall respect the essence of the fundamental rights and freedoms and **shall be a necessary and proportionate measure** in a democratic society **to fulfil purposes of public interest in the area of legitimate scientific and societal objectives.**

3) Intellectual property (IP) rights protection

Secondary use of (personal and non-personal) electronic health data subject to IP rights

3) Intellectual property (IP) rights protection

IP governance rules

- Article 52(1): “**Electronic health data protected by intellectual property rights, trade secrets or covered by the regulatory data protection right [.] shall be made available for secondary use.**”
- Article 52(2): “**Health data holders shall inform the health data access body [“HDAB”]** of any electronic health data containing content or information protected by intellectual property rights, trade secrets or covered by the regulatory data protection right [.]”
- Article 52(3): “**Health data access bodies shall take all specific appropriate and proportionate measures**, including of a legal, organisational and technical nature, they deem necessary to protect the intellectual property rights, trade secrets or the regulatory data protection right [.]”
- Article 52(5): “**Where** the granting of access to electronic health data for **secondary use entails a serious risk of infringing** intellectual property rights, trade secrets or the regulatory data protection right [.] which cannot be addressed in a satisfactory manner, the **health data access body shall refuse access to the health data applicant to such data.**”

Thank you for your attention!

For questions and potential collaborations:

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<https://pravri.uniri.hr/en/project/dgip-ceds/>